

Център за върхови постижения „Наследство БГ“
Centre of Excellence 'Heritage BG'

БЮЛЕТИН „НАСЛЕДСТВО БГ“ – НАУЧНИ ИЗВЕСТИЯ
BULLETIN 'HERITAGE BG' – RESEARCH ANNOUNCEMENTS

Рецензирано издание в два броя годишно
Peer-reviewed periodical in two issues per year

Съставители на броя
Диляна Ботева-Боянова, Юлия Цветкова
и Лили Грозданова

Compiled and edited by
Dilyana Boteva-Boyanova, Julia Tzvetkova
and Lily Grozdanova

Година IV, брой 7 / Year IV, issue 7th
Sofia, 2024

Наследство БГ
Година IV, брой 7 / Year IV, issue 7th
Sofia, 2024

Главен редактор проф. д.н. Емануел Мутафов
Заместник-главен редактор проф. дфн Оля Харизанова

Editor in Chief Prof. DSc Emmanuel Moutafov
Deputy Editor in Chief Prof. DSc Olya Harizanova

Редакционна колегия

проф. д.н. Емануел Мутафов (главен редактор), чл.-кор. проф. дин Иван Илчев (председател на редколегията), проф. дфн Оля Харизанова (зам. главен редактор), проф. д-р Стоян Недков (НИИГГ-БАН), проф. дфн Албена Ангелова-Георгиева (ИЕФЕМ-БАН), проф. д-р Фантина Рангелова (УАСГ), гл. ас. д-р Нели Ганчева (КМНЦ-БАН), проф. д.н. Бистра Димитрова (НСА), проф. д.н. Иван Кралов (ТУ-София), доц. д-р Елка Димитрова (ИЛ-БАН), чл.-кор. проф. дин Александър Костов (ИБЦТ-БАН)

Editorial Board

Prof. DSc Emmanuel Moutafov (Editor in Chief), Prof. DSc Ivan Ilchev (President of the Editorial Board), Prof. DSc Olya Harizanova (Deputy Editor in Chief), Prof. Dr Stoyan Nedkov (NIGGG-BAS), Prof. DSc Albena Angelova-Georgieva (IEFSEM-BAS), Prof. Dr Fantina Rangelova (UASEG), Assist. Prof. Dr Neli Gancheva (CMRC-BAS), Prof. DSc Bistra Dimitrova (NSA), Prof. Dr Ivan Kralov (TU-Sofia), Assoc. Prof. Dr Elka Dimitrova (IL-BAS), Prof. DSc Alexander Kostov (IBSCT-BAS)

Международна редакционна колегия / International Advisory Board

Assoc. Prof. Dr Ines Grigorescu (Romania), Prof. DSc Irina Sedakova (Russian Federation), Prof. Dr Damian Kashkalev (USA), Prof. DSc Aleksander Naunow (Italy/Poland), Prof. DSc Roumiana Tsenkova (Japan), Prof. Dr Pedja Filipović (Serbia), Assoc. Prof. Dr Alexander Iliev (USA), Dr Sophoklis Christophoridis (Greece), Prof. DSc Harald Heppner (Austria), Dr Habil Henrike Schmidt (Germany), Dr Maria Litina (Greece)

Редакционен екип

проф. д.н. Емануел Мутафов (ИИИЗк-БАН), чл.-кор. проф. дин Иван Илчев (СУ), проф. дфн Оля Харизанова (СУ)

Editorial Staff

Prof. DSc Emmanuel Moutafov (IAS-BAS), Prof. DSc Ivan Ilchev (Sofia University), Prof. DSc Olya Harizanova (Sofia University)

Издател

© Сдружение „Център за върхови постижения „Наследство БГ“,
София 1000, ул. „Ген. Йосиф В. Гурко“ № 7, 2024
yearbook@nasledstvo.bg

Publisher

© Association Centre for Excellence 'Heritage BG',
Sofia 1000, 7 General Iosif V. Gurko Street, 2024
yearbook@nasledstvo.bg

ISSN 2815-3138 (Print)
ISSN 2815-3316 (Online)

Научни известия

Бюлетин „Наследство БГ“, Година IV, брой 7, 2024

Research Announcements

Bulletin ‘Heritage BG’, Year IV, Issue 7th, 2024

**RESEARCHES OF ANCIENT THRACE
BETWEEN TRADITIONALITY
AND MODERNITY:
THEORETICAL ASPECTS AND
SCIENTIFIC METHODOLOGY**

**ИЗСЛЕДВАНИЯТА НА ДРЕВНА ТРАКИЯ
МЕЖДУ ТРАДИЦИОННОСТ
И МОДЕРНОСТ:
ТЕОРЕТИЧНИ АСПЕКТИ И НАУЧНА
МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ**

Contents / Съдържание

Preface5

SECTION ANCIENT HISTORY

Analyzing the Texts of the Ancient (and not only the Ancient) Authors: Some Methodological Aspects

Dilyana Boteva-Boyanova (Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridks’)6

The ‘Early State’ and its Main Characteristics

Tsvetelin Stepanov (Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridks’)14

The History of Ancient Thrace, a Field for Methodological Experimentation, Historiographical Deconstruction and Epistemological Reflection

Alienor Rufin Solas (Lorraine University)20

Tertullian, de Anima 46 and the ‘Dreaming Saturn’: A Hidden Testimony to the Myth of Zalmoxis in Aristotle’s Lost Eudemus

Franziska van Buren (KU Leuven)26

SECTION ARCHAEOLOGY

The Employment of Digital Tools in the Study of Ancient Thrace

Despoina Tsiafaki, Yiannis Mourthos, Melpomeni Karta, Natasa Michailidou (Athena Research Center)34

Unlocking Strategies of Visual Communication in Zones of Cultural Interaction: Opportunities and Challenges in the Digital Age

Veronika Sossau (Basel University)46

<i>Intervisibility Among the Thousand Mounds of the Yambol Province</i> Adela Sobotkova (Aarhus University)	54
<i>From Deultum to DigiDeultum</i> Lyudmil Vagalinski (NAIM-BAS)	62
<i>Digital Digging on the Molyvoti, Thrace, Archaeological Project: IDig and a New Web Application</i> Marina Tasaklaki (Ionian University), Nathan Arrington (Princeton University)	70
SECTION EPIGRAPHY & LINGUISTICS	
<i>Measuring the Otherness: Non-Greeks among Greeks in Apollonia Pontica</i> Mirena Slavova (Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridksi)	82
<i>Ethnē Thrakōn in Ancient Greek and Latin Authors – What’s in a Name?</i> Maria Gabriella Parissaki (National Hellenic Research Foundation, Institute for Historical Research)	94
<i>Structured Metadata for the Digital Corpora of Ancient Epigraphic Monuments from Bulgaria</i> Dimitar Iliev (Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridksi)	100
<i>Unraveling the Threads of Thrace: A Text Mining Expedition in Pliny’s Natural History</i> Kristian Simeonov (Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridksi)	108
SECTION NUMISMATICS	
<i>Thracian Numismatics in the Light of the SILVER Website (Die Studies Database and Greek Overstrikes Database)</i> François de Callataÿ (Royal Library of Belgium, Free University of Brussels)	114
<i>Numismatic Databases: History of Bulgarian Interdisciplinary Studies</i> Valentina Grigorova-Gencheva (Fibank, VUZF)	128
<i>Grasping the Invisible. An Approach to Frontier Dynamics between Thrace and Macedonia through Digital Numismatics and Archaeology</i> Hristina Ivanova-Anaplioti (University of Zurich)	136
<i>‘Measuring’ the Chronology of the so-called Moesian Countermarks</i> Vladislav Zhivkov (NAIM-BAS), Varbin Varbanov (NAIM-BAS, RHM-Ruse)	148
SECTION ARCHAEOOMETRY	
<i>Silver Coins from Ancient Cities of Aegean Thrace through XRF Analysis</i> Marina Tasaklaki (Ionian University), Nerantzis Nerantzis (Université libre de Bruxelles)	158
<i>Studies on Ancient Metalworking Techniques: Preliminary Report</i> Svenja Simon (Saarland University)	168
List of the additional images	175

PREFACE

The studies of Antiquity in Bulgarian historical science have a long tradition since the foundation of Sofia University in 1888. Unfortunately, in the last decades these studies have been largely devoid of scientific debate in terms of theoretical and methodological framework. The new millennium has added to the traditional disciplines of history, archaeology, epigraphy and numismatics other key aspects of the interdisciplinary approach, such as archaeometric studies and digital humanities.

The 'Measuring Ancient Thrace' project funded by BNSF (КП-06-Н50/3 from 30.11.2020), has aimed to provoke a methodological debate on the place of the digital technologies and the methods of exact sciences in the research of the history and culture of ancient Thrace at a theoretical and practical level. The created wide network of scholarly contacts and research highlights focused on the lands of ancient Thrace provoked the organization of an international scientific conference entitled 'Researches of Ancient Thrace between Traditionality and Modernity: Theoretical Aspects and Scientific Methodology' (<https://digithrace.uni-sofia.bg/digithrace-conference/>). It took place on April 11th – 13th 2024 at the Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski with the financial support of the BNSF (project № КП-06-МНФ/44 from 19.12.2023).

The aim of the conference was to provoke a scientific debate on traditional and new methodological approaches to the study of Antiquity and Ancient Thrace in particular. The discussion was innovative for Bulgaria and for the research of ancient Thracian history and culture, since after the establishment of Thracology as a historical discipline in the early 1970s such deliberate debates have not been held in Bulgarian scholarly community.

The conference focused on the impact of the digital age on the understanding and interpretation of ancient Thrace. The provoked topic concerns the theory and methodology in the four key disciplines of historical knowledge - ancient history, archaeology, epigraphy, numismatics, but also in archaeometric research, and their relationship to digital technologies. The program of the conference is available at <https://digithrace.uni-sofia.bg/digithrace-conference/>

In the present volume, 19 of the conference presentations are published; they systematize the directions of development and present the new trends in the research of ancient Thrace in the 21st century. If no other indications, summaries and keywords sent solely in English have been translated into Bulgarian by Dilyana Boteva; the editors are hopeful that these translations are all correct.

The editors express their sincere gratitude to the Association Centre for Excellence 'Heritage BG' for the kind offer to publish the proceedings of the conference in its Research Announcements.

The Employment of Digital Tools in the Study of Ancient Thrace

**Despoina Tsiadaki, Yiannis Mourthos,
Melpomeni Karta, Natasa Michailidou**
Athena Research Center

Abstract: *The employment of digital tools in the study of Ancient Thrace can enhance our understanding of the region. The vast volume of analog data available underscores the need for interconnected datasets via repositories. Digitizing various data types, including archaeological finds, literary works, and inscriptions, promotes scholarly collaboration. Moreover, the study of Thrace, a region rich in history and mythology, also benefits from research with GIS tools that enable quantitative analyses, study of people and object diffusion, trade networks, and landscape exploration. These technological advancements revolutionize archaeological research, potentially driving economic growth and influencing cultural policies.*

Keywords: Athena RC; repositories; Attic pottery; mythology; GIS; networks; landscape

Ключови думи: Изследователски център Athena; репозиториуми; атическа керамика; митология; ГИС; мрежи; ландшафт

Dr Despoina Tsiadaki is an archaeologist, Research Director and Head of the Culture and Creative Industries Department at the Athena Research Center with interests in Classical Archaeology, Pottery Studies, Archaeological Sciences, Museology, Digital Humanities.

E-mail: tsiadaki@athenarc.gr
ORCID: 0000-0003-4948-255X

Dr Yiannis Mourthos is a classical archaeologist with expertise on social memory and identity; Scientific Associate of the ILSP at the Athena RC on digital archaeology.

E-mail: jmourthos@athenarc.gr
ORCID: 0000-0001-6693-1201

Melpomeni Karta is a classical archaeologist; Scientific Associate of the ILSP at the Athena RC on digital archaeology, documentation of cultural heritage, restorator.

E-mail: melpomek@athenarc.gr
ORCID: 0000-0001-8302-5665

Natasa Michailidou is an archaeologist-museologist; Scientific Associate of the ILSP at the Athena RC on digital tools for the documentation of cultural heritage.

E-mail: amixaili@athenarc.gr

INTRODUCTION:

ANCIENT THRACE GOES DIGIT

Archaeological research is a longtime procedure, despite the site or the topic of particular interest. As a discipline also has a long tradition going back a few centuries. In this investigation and study of the past (times, cultures, sites etc.) aiming at its better understanding, Archaeology has employed a great number of approaches and procedures. In reality, Archaeology has adapted and adopted the available tools and methods following the trends of the time. During the last decades digital technologies have significantly revised archaeological research and documentation methods with the study of ancient Thrace being no exception.

The employment of digital tools in the study of Ancient Thrace can significantly enhance our knowledge of the region as well as contribute to its understanding and promotion. Digital archaeology and its widely accessible outcomes not only revolutionize research but also potentially may lead to economic growth and to influence cultural policies. The various research projects and publications regarding Ancient Thrace are increasingly adopting these technologies, utilizing the latest advancements in the related fields.

The aim of this paper is to present some indicative examples of the interdisciplinary work done by the Institute of Language and Speech Processing (ILSP) regarding the study of ancient Thrace. Combining digital with traditional methods, it attempts to contribute to the production of new knowledge for the region as well as to make the outcomes of its research widely known and accessible. Three thematic areas are chosen to be briefly presented here: a) the collection and organization of the sources used (repositories) as the foundation for any study and research, b) the interdisciplinary approach chosen for the examination of a representative category of material (Attic pottery), and c) mythology as connecting link between Greece and Thrace. To those should be added the contribution of Geospatial research in archaeology (GIS).

COLLECTING AND ORGANIZING RESEARCH LITERATURE WITH DIGITAL TOOLS

The extensive scientific literature on ancient Thrace covers multiple languages, themes, and scientific fields. However, there is a significant need for comprehensive digital tools to organize, make accessible, and distribute this wealth. To address this, efforts are made to create centralized repositories of literature cat-

egorized by specific sites, periods, and topics. In these repositories, each publication tagged with keywords, facilitates targeted searches and improves accessibility. Moreover, committed to viability, these repositories are regularly updated to reflect ongoing discourse and state-of-the-art in the field.

Thus, for example, the **Archaeological Research in the North Aegean (ARENA)** repository¹ focuses on the extensive archaeological bibliography of Aegean Thrace (**Fig. 1**), covering a period from the 8th century BC to 31 BC. Up to date, over 5,900 titles have been compiled regarding more than 540 ancient sites, thus creating a valuable bibliographical repository, with advanced search tools that allow users to easily explore the collected information. The repository also includes ancient texts, inscriptions, and educational material related to Aegean Thrace².

Likewise, the **Attic POTtery in Thrace (AtticPOT)**³ addressed the need for digital tools to aid the study of Attic painted pottery found in ancient Thrace. A digital repository was developed, encompassing Attic pottery and specialized literature, cataloging approximately 8,700 references about 215 ancient sites. AtticPOT offers researchers resources on the distribution and significance of Attic pottery in the region, providing digital tools that allow users to navigate and extract information, enhancing the

Figure 1. The interactive map of ARENA project.

¹ <http://arena.athenarc.gr/>

² Tsiafaki and Michailidou 2019; Michailidou, Evangelidis and Tsiafaki 2020; Tsiafaki et al. 2020.

³ <https://atticpot.athenarc.gr/index.php/en/>; <https://atticpot.athenarc.gr/repo/en/>

Figure 2. The AtticPOT interactive map.

availability of the material⁴.

A third case is **Mythotopia: Mythological Routes in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace project**⁵. Mythotopia highlights the region’s cultural and touristic richness through extensive recording, and mapping of ancient myths related to Thrace. It developed a specialized digital repository containing numerous Greek and Latin texts and ancient artworks depicting 36 region-specific myths, thus creating over 200 references, providing diverse ancient literary sources on Thracian mythology.

STUDYING ATTIC POTTERY IN THRACE

After setting up the base of the study, namely building the repository, the next step is to focus on a specific topic, such as for example the Attic pottery. Therefore, aligning with initiatives like BAPD, the AtticPOT employed the developed repository as a base to map and better understand the presence of the Attic vases in ancient Thrace⁶. It focused on various scientific and artistic aspects of Attic pottery, which dominated in the ancient Greek world from the

6th century BC onwards. After collecting the published painted pottery in the examined region, AtticPOT explored the distribution, uses, and preferences for Attic vases across ancient Thrace. Namely it covered sites located in a geographical area shared nowadays between Greece, Bulgaria, Turkey, and Romania. Combining in its methodology traditional with ICT tools, it proceeded to the examination of a large set of vases dated from the 6th to the 4th century BC. Furthermore, studying the presence of Attic pottery in various contexts, AtticPOT aimed to uncover exchange networks, usage patterns, and local preferences⁷.

AtticPOT’s repository hosts published data coming from a great range of sources (i.e. proceedings, reports, catalogues), covering simultaneously various contexts and collections. To manage the extensive material, researchers may navigate the vase records using browse, search, sort, and export functionalities. An interactive digital map (Fig. 2) provides a dynamic visualization of the vase distribution, filtered through comprehensive search criteria, including shapes, iconography, painters, potters, etc.

⁴ Avramidou and Tsiadaki 2022; Chiotti, Avramidou and Tsiadaki 2019; Mourthos and Tsiadaki 2022:217-218; Michailidou et al. forthcoming; Tsiadaki, Michailidou and Chiotti 2020; Tsiadaki et al. forthcoming.

⁵ <https://mythotopia.eu/>

⁶ Tsiadaki 2022.

⁷ Michailidou 2022.

Figure 3. AtticPOT quantitative analysis tool.

Moreover, advanced research tools (Fig. 3) allow users to perform detailed analyses, saving favorites, and conducting quantitative analyses to uncover patterns and trends. Despite the project's official end, the ongoing process has amassed a robust collection of over 5,400 vases, approximately 8,700 bibliographical entries, and information from 215 sites across Greece, Turkey, Bulgaria, and Romania, thus enabling a more accessible and detailed study of Attic pottery across the region⁸.

Using these tools for the research and study AtticPOT resulted in interesting observations and conclusions. For example, a focus and preference on a select range of vessel types (e.g., kraters, lekythoi) within the Attic pottery repertoire has been observed, which could be related to their function and context⁹. The study of a specific shape provided information on a deeper level. For instance, one of the most popular shapes, kraters, are found throughout the region, but their presence varies significantly in terms of quantity. Moreover, a great number of them have been unearthed in coastal sites. This could be due to the fact that coastal sites are

likely more extensively excavated or might be related to historical factors associated, for example, with networks and routes of commerce. A great number of the kraters do not preserve clear finding contexts. Those, however, with known excavation sites mostly come from cemeteries and sanctuaries, predominantly from the 5th and 4th centuries BC. Unless future published data alter this observation, this pattern highlights the fact that they may have played a clear role in funerary and religious traditions, at least in specific areas¹⁰.

The other most popular shape of Attic painted pottery in ancient Thrace is lekythos. As regards the 4th century lekythoi, most of them are found in coastal regions, but it is worth mentioning that a significant number of them come from just five sites or has unknown provenance. To the latter may be due, as it has been suggested in the case of the kraters, that these sites could be better excavated. Taking again into consideration the kraters, we may assume that coastal Greek colonies could have served as major hubs for Attic pottery trade. Worth of note is that nearly all lekythoi from known

⁸ Tsiafaki, Michailidou and Chioti 2020; Michailidou 2022; Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming; Michailidou 2022.

⁹ Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming.

¹⁰ Avramidou, Tsiafaki 2022; Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming.

Figure 4. Context of the Attic 4th century lekythoi of Thrace.

contexts are discovered in cemeteries (**Fig. 4**), highlighting their role in funerary practices and rituals. Very few are found in sanctuaries, possibly as offerings, indicating a limited role in religious practices. The same limited presence applies so far to civic and domestic contexts¹¹.

Apart from shapes, the next important aspect of Attic painted pottery is iconography. The examination of the general distribution of popular iconographic themes (6th-4th century BC) in the AtticPOT repository resulted in several interesting trends. Floral and decorative motifs seem to prevail, while depictions of animal and Dionysiac scenes are also prominent, along with conversations, mythical creatures, domestic scenes, and warriors¹². Dionysiac scenes stand out, spreading across both coastal and inland Thrace and appearing on various vessel types. Many Dionysiac scenes are found on sherds of unidentified vessels and often come from unknown or unpublished contexts. Those with known contexts are primarily discovered in cemeteries and sanctuaries. Chronologically, Dionysiac scenes are most prevalent in the 5th

century BC, followed by the 4th century BC, with limited occurrences in the 6th century BC¹³.

Technologies like those employed for the AtticPOT implementation facilitate detailed analysis of specific case studies, whether individually or comparatively. For instance, in exploring the contexts of 4th century lekythoi, distinct archaeological sites emerge as focal points for understanding the distribution and significance of these artifacts. One notable site is Mesembria-Zone, whose necropolis has yielded a substantial quantity of 4th century lekythoi¹⁴. Excavations in the necropolis of Ainos have also uncovered numerous 4th century lekythoi, highlighting the city's role as a market and distribution hub for Attic pottery during this period¹⁵. Moving to northern Thrace, near the ancient colony of Apollonia Pontica, Kalfata, cemetery, typical of Greek cities and colonies, has yielded numerous 4th century lekythoi¹⁶.

In summary, the AtticPOT work exemplifies the transformative impact of ICT in classical archaeology, particularly regarding ancient Thrace. The developed digital tools provide the researchers the possibility to analyze extensive datasets, uncover intricate patterns, and gain nuanced insights into archaeological inquiries. ICT tools used in combination with traditional methods may facilitate systematic investigation into pottery typology, chronology, provenance, and cultural context, providing valuable resources. For sharing its research findings and engaging the scholarly community, AtticPOT adopted a hybrid approach of dissemination, both "traditional" and digital, organizing workshops that fostered collaboration among researchers from Greece, Turkey, and Bulgaria. This interstate effort culminated in a printed volume featuring contributions from esteemed scholars, showcasing diverse perspectives on the topic¹⁷, as well as non-predicted in advance outcomes, such as a comprehensive presentation on the history of research into Attic deco-

¹¹ Tsiafaki, Mourthos, Michailidou forthcoming.

¹² Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming; Michailidou 2022: 48-51.

¹³ Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming.

¹⁴ E.g. Archaeological Museum of Komotini (MK/AGK 3557); Iliopoulou 2015: 61-71; Iliopoulou and Pardalidou 2022; Tsiafaki, Mourthos, Michailidou forthcoming.

¹⁵ Şahin 2016; Tsiafaki, Mourthos, Michailidou forthcoming.

¹⁶ Damyanov 2022; Tsiafaki, Mourthos, Michailidou forthcoming.

¹⁷ Tsiafaki et al. 2022.

rated pottery in Bulgaria¹⁸.

The issue of iconography, as a key aspect for extracting further knowledge on the region of ancient Thrace and its inhabitants, is also significant for the next thematic area examined here, that of the Thracian myths.

STUDYING THE ICONOGRAPHY OF THRACIAN MYTHS

Thrace boasts a rich mythological legacy, with numerous Greco-Roman artifacts coming from various eras to depict Thracian myths and to be housed in collections worldwide. Those myths are the topic of **Mythotopia** focused on exploring and promoting Thrace's mythological wealth along with its exploitation for tourism strengthening. In this case there is an integration of the traditional methods of classical studies (philology, archaeology) with ICT, leveraging tools like GIS, repositories, and interactive platforms. From the archaeological perspective -of interest here-, there is a significant number of ancient artifacts to meet contemporary tourism demands by creating immersive and educational experiences centered on Thracian myths. Moreover, by studying the iconography of these myths, researchers gain insights into artistic perceptions, cultural practices, religious

beliefs, regional identity, and interactions with the Greco-Roman world.

At the heart of Mythotopia is a repository containing material related to the 36 selected myths related to Thrace. The repository includes over 300 ancient texts and references, along with more than 300 artifacts associated with these myths. Integration of multimedia and POIs enhances engagement, providing contextual information for more immersive experiences and understanding of Thracian myths. These sources encompass a wide array of philological, archaeological, and scientific materials. Central to the repository are Greek and Latin texts, which cover diverse genres such as epic poetry, historiography, tragedy, and other literary forms, from the works of approximately 95 ancient writers. All this information is available to the researchers as well as the visitors, tourists, and general audience.

Moreover, Mythotopia extensively utilizes archaeological artifacts of Greek and Roman origin. Decorated vessels, particularly Attic pottery adorned with mythological imagery, contribute to understanding the appeal Thracian myths had to Greek audiences¹⁹ and the influence of Greek imports on Thracian taste. Sculptural artifacts (**Fig. 5a**) offer visual representa-

a

b

Figure 5. a. Orpheus, Euridice and Hermes. Marble relief, 1st century BC-1st c. AD, Louvre museum (Paris) no Ma 854; **b.** Orpheus taming the animals. Mosaic floor from Miletus, 180-200 AD. Antikensammlung der Staatlichen Museen (Berlin), no. 72.

¹⁸ Banev forthcoming.

¹⁹ Tsiadaki 1998; Tsiadaki 2016.

Figure 5. c. Orpheus playing his lyre. Gold stater of Lampsakos, 387-334 BC. Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen (Berlin), no. 18215944; d. The murder of Orpheus on a gold-plated silver rhyton, 420-410 BC. Vassil Bojkov Collection, Sofia.

tions of mythological themes and characters, providing insights into artistic interpretations of Thracian myths and their significance in ancient iconography. Thracian myths are also depicted on mosaics (Fig. 5b) and coins (Fig. 5c), as well as on some elaborate and rare items, such as a gold-plated silver rhyton from Sofia (Fig. 5d). These artifacts serve as primary evidence as well as visual stimuli, offering material manifestations of mythological themes and characters. Selected photographs of these artifacts, used after permission, enrich the provided resources²⁰.

The rich material of Mythotopia draws exclusively from scientific publications, repositories, and official websites of institutions. This material fueled the development of a user-friendly platform and mobile application that integrates diverse information related to Thracian myths and cultural landscapes, offers touristic routes, and serves as an educational resource. Voiceover functionality to aid users with visual impairments ensures inclusivity and broadens access. Moreover, Mythotopia extends its impact beyond tourism by providing educational content aimed at secondary school pupils. Finally, Mythotopia also prioritizes “traditional” dissemination, through participation in conferences and

the publication of a collective volume²¹, pointing again to a combination of digital with analog.

GEOSPATIAL RESEARCH AND THE AEGIS LAB

Established in 2020, the **Archaeological GIS Laboratory (AeGIS Athena)**²² marks a significant advancement in the study of cultural landscapes and human-environment interactions. Building on previous expertise of GIS technologies²³, AeGIS Athena serves as a hub for high-resolution documentation, mapping analysis, and 3D visualization. It supports diverse research inquiries with flexibility, utilizing both advanced and open-source GIS tools like QGIS to explore various perspectives and approaches in archaeological research. For instance, by integrating **symbolology and quantitative analysis** techniques with the extensive dataset from AtticPOT, the distribution and characteristics of Attic pottery in ancient Thrace was further explored. In one case study, the utilization of custom-made symbols to visualize the occurrences of rare pottery shapes across various Thrace sites (Fig. 6) facilitated a comparative examination of spatial distribution patterns, providing nuanced insights into the

²⁰ *Vacalopoulou et al. 2023.*

²¹ *Tsiafaki et al. 2023.*

²² <https://aegis.athenarc.gr/>

²³ *Tsiafaki, Evangelidis 2006.*

Figure 6. Map showing the distribution of rare shapes of Attic pottery, using custom made symbols showcasing the shape, the context and the date.

geographical and temporal trends of these rare shapes²⁴.

Moreover, the same integration yielded fruitful results in another case study. This time the focus was on Attic pottery found on sites located in Aegean Thrace, with emphasis on the area of Pistyros-Pontolivado²⁵. By employing spatial analysis techniques and customized symbology, the distribution of Attic pottery was systematically mapped out, thus allowing the engagement

in discussions regarding trade networks, cultural interactions, and stylistic preferences prevalent in the region during the 6th to 4th centuries BC. Through the visualization and analysis of Attic pottery distribution, valuable insights into the dynamics shaping the exchange and diffusion of material culture in this area were retrieved. To effectively communicate these complex archaeological patterns, the AtticPOT employed symbology techniques including heat maps, which use color

Figure 7. Heat map of the total distribution of Attic pottery (6th-4th century BC) in the area around Pontolivado.

²⁴ Mourthos, Tsiafaki 2022.

²⁵ For the site see Papadopoulos 2022.

Figure 8. Map combining a heat map, Nearest Neighbor Network analysis of AtticPOT data and the Roman road network in the area of ancient Thrace.

intensity to illustrate the density or frequency of phenomena. The analysis of AtticPOT data with GIS software generated **heat maps with quantitative symbology** examining the distribution and quantities of Attic pottery (Fig. 7)²⁶.

Combining the data from the AtticPOT repository and GIS software, trade routes and networks were explored by analyzing the distribution of rare shapes in ancient Thrace. However, our current focus includes a Five-node Nearest Neighbor Network analysis across the entire AtticPOT dataset to map connectivity between archaeological sites. Interestingly, our findings align significant portions of this network with the Roman road network from the Barrington Atlas in ArcGIS Hub (Fig. 8). This correspondence possibly suggests a continuity in trade routes from the Archaic and Classical periods to Roman times, highlighting enduring economic and cultural exchanges over centuries.

Finally comes **landscape archaeology** and the study of natural and anthropogenic landscapes in Aegean Thrace. Using data provided by the Lab of Applied Soil Science of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, AeGIS Lab created soil maps to investigate the influence of environmental and cultural factors on ancient economy and settlement patterns. The study

focused on the area of Vafeika, Abdera, and Bergopolis (Koutso), early Thracian sites situated in areas affected by the river Kosynthos. By analyzing soil composition within buffer zones around these sites, the research explored how alluvial processes and extensive fluvial landscapes impacted ancient economy and settlement patterns. The findings underscored the pivotal role of fluvial landscapes in shaping the distinct economic activities of the region²⁷.

CONCLUSIONS

The utilization of digital tools in studying Ancient Thrace offers transformative insights, particularly in managing vast analog data sources. Establishing interconnected repositories and aggregators for archaeological finds, literary texts, inscriptions, and research bibliographies is crucial for preservation and collaboration among scholars. The rich history, mythology, and tourism potential of Thrace make it a compelling super-region. GIS tools enable quantitative analyses, facilitating studies on population movements, trade networks, and landscape dynamics. These technological advancements revolutionize archaeological research, enhancing our understanding of Thracian culture and history while potentially influ-

²⁶ A couple of them will be published in *Tsiafaki and Amoiridou* forthcoming.

²⁷ *Tsiafaki, Evangelidis* 2022.

encing economic growth and cultural policies.

To truly unlock the potential of digital tools in studying ancient Thrace, collaboration is necessary. It's crucial for institutions and researchers of the states that share the lands of ancient Thrace to join forces. The rich and complex her-

itage of Thrace can only be fully appreciated through a cooperative effort in collecting, analyzing, and sharing data, a teamwork that will not only deepen our understanding of the region's history and cultures but will also help preserve and interpret them in a more integrated way.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

Avramidou, Tsiafaki 2022a: Avramidou, Amalia, Despoina Tsiafaki. Preliminary Results of the Research Project Attic Pottery in Thrace. In: The Proceedings of the 13th International Congress of Thracology "Ancient Thrace: Myth and Reality", Kazanlak, September 3-7, 2017, volume 1, Sofia, 35-44.

Avramidou, Tsiafaki 2022b: Avramidou, Amalia, Despoina Tsiafaki. Attic Kraters and Pelikai from Ancient Thrace. In: Greek and Etruscan Vases: Shapes and Markets: Panel 5.15, (Archaeology and Economy in the Ancient World: Proceedings of the 19th International Congress of Classical Archaeology, Cologne/Bonn 2018, Band 34), (ed. Dimitris Paleothodoros). Heidelberg, 57-75.

Banev forthcoming: Banev, Guentcho. I érvna tis attikís graptís keramikís sti Voulgaría: aparkhés, poría kai sinisphorá. Mía episkópisi tis vivliographías me aphormí to érgo AtticPOT. – Mare Ponticum.

Bikakis et al. 2023: Bikakis, Nikos, Giorgos Giannopoulos, Nikos Sidiropoulos, Christina Flouda, Athanasios Doupas, Voula Giouli, Panagiotis Karioris, Paraskevi Botini, Anna Vacalopoulou, Gregory Stainhaouer. Exposing geospatial cultural heritage content in map-based applications. In: Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on Big Data Visual Exploration and Analytics co-located with EDBT/ICDT 2023 Joint Conference (March 28-31, 2023), Ioannina, GR (BigVis) (eds. George Fletcher, Verena Kantere). Available at: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3379/BigVis2023_700.pdf.

Chioti, Avramidou, Tsiafaki 2019: Chioti, Eirini, Amalia Avramidou, Despoina Tsiafaki. The AtticPOT project – Attic PO(ttery in) T(hrace). – BeJA, 9/2, 293-294.

Damyantov 2022: Damyanov, Margarit. Attic painted pottery on the West Pontic Coast: Across the gaps. In: Tsiafaki et al. 2022, 288-306.

Giouli et al. 2022a: Giouli, Voula, Anna Vacalopoulou, Nikos Sidiropoulos, Christina Flouda, Athanasios Doupas, Gregory Stainhaouer. From mythos to logos: A bilingual thesaurus tailored to meet user's needs within the ecosystem of cultural tourism. In: Dictionaries and Society. Proceedings of the XX EURALEX International Congress, September 7, 2022, (eds. Annette Klosa-Kückelhaus, Stefan Engelberg, Christine Möhrs, Petra Storjohann). Mannheim, 625-634.

Giouli et al. 2022b: Giouli, Voula, Anna Vacalopoulou, Nikolaos Sidiropoulos, Christina Flouda, Athanasios Doupas, Giorgos Giannopoulos, Nikos Bikakis, Vassilis Kaffes, Gregory Stainhaouer. Placing multi-modal, and multi-lingual Data in the Humanities Domain on the Map: the Mythotopia Geo-tagged Corpus. In: Proceedings of the 13th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2022), Marseille, 20-25 June 2022, (eds. Nicoletta Calzolari, Frédéric Béchet, Philippe Blache, Khalid Choukri, Christopher Cieri, Thierry Declerck, Sara Goggi, Hitoshi Isahara, Bente Maegaard, Joseph Mariani, Hélène Mazo, Jan Odiijk, Stelios Piperidis). Paris, 2859-2864.

Graser 2016: Graser, Anita. Learning QGIS. Birmingham-Mumbai.

Iliopoulou 2015: Iliopoulou, Sofi. Arkhaía Zóni IIIa. To nekrotaphío. Taphiká éthima kai praktikés, Komotini.

Iliopoulou and Pardalidou 2022: Iliopoulou, Sofi, Chrysafenia Pardalidou. Attikí graptí keramikí apó tin arkhaía Zóni. In: Tsiafaki et al., 2022, 228-244.

Michailidou 2022: Michailidou, Natasa. I attikí keramikí "sta khéria" tis psiphikís tekhnoloyías: to érgo AtticPOT se evrítero plaísio. In: Tsiafaki et al. 2022, 38-56.

Michailidou et al. forthcoming: Michailidou, Natasa, Despoina Tsiafaki, Kostas Stavroglou, Ioannis Mourthos, Meliana Karta, Markos Dimitzas. AtticPOT: a borderless approach for studying Attic painted pottery in ancient Thrace. In: Computer applications and quantitative methods in Archaeology (CAA), June 14-18, 2021 (online event).

Michailidou, Evangelidis, Tsiafaki 2020: Michailidou, Natasa, Vassilis Evangelidis, Despoina Tsiafaki. ARENA EDU: Creating Digital Educational Content for Twenty First Century Archaeological Visits. In: Education VIA Culture: An International Conference on the Applications of Cultural Heritage in Education, December 18-20, 2020, Thessaloniki, Greece (through Zoom).

Mourthos and Tsiafaki 2022: Mourthos, Yianis, Despoina Tsiafaki. Contextualizing rare shapes of Athenian Kerameikos from coastal and inland Thrace (6th–4th c. BC): an approach through the AtticPOT repository. – BeJA 12/2: 217-243.

Papadopoulos 2022: Papadopoulos, Stratis. Sistimatikí anaskaphí Pistírou: i próti pentaetía. In Ídia i mními yinámeni parón – To arkhaioloyikó

érgo ton ephorión arkhaiotítton katá ti khronikí período 2011-2019 (ed. Eleni Kotsou). Athens, 458-462.

Şahin 2016: Şahin, Reyhan. Red-figure Pottery of the 4th Century BC from Ainos in Thrace: The Final Phase of the Classical Tradition in Eastern Thrace. In: Traditions and Innovations. Tracking the Development of Pottery from the Late Classical to the Early Imperial Periods. Proceedings of the 1st Conference of IARPotHP, Berlin, November 2013, 7th-10th, IARPotHP 1, (eds. Sarah Japp, Patricia Kögler). Wien, 2016, 329-340.

Tsiafaki 1998: Tsiafaki, Despoina. I Thráki stin attikí ikonographía tou 5ou aióna p. Kh. Prosengísis stis skhésis Athínas kai Thrákis. Komotini.

Tsiafaki 2016: Tsiafaki, Despoina. Ancient Thrace and Thracians through the Athenian eyes. – *Thracia* 21: 261–282.

Tsiafaki 2022: Tsiafaki, Despoina. AtticPOT. H Athinaikí parousía stin arkháia Thráki (6os – 4os ai. p. Kh.). In: Tsiafaki et al. 2022, 57-76.

Tsiafaki and Amoiridou forthcoming: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Kostantia Amoiridou. Prótes paratirísis yia tin próimi isigméni keramikí tis aiyaiaikís Pistírou. In *Aiyaiaikí Pistiros* (ed. Stratis Papadopoulos).

Tsiafaki et al. 2020: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Kostas Stavroglou, Natasa Michailidou, Chairi Kiourt, Yiannis Mourthos. I arkhaiologyiké érevna sti Tháso mésa apó to psiphiaikó apothetírío ARENA. In: 8o Simpósio Thasiakón Meletón, 12-14 Oktovríou 2019 (Thasiaká 20). Kavala, 443-463.

Tsiafaki et al. 2022: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Amalia Avramidou, Natasa Michailidou, Ioannis Mourthos, Meliana Karta, eds. AtticPOT: Attic Painted Pottery in Ancient Thrace (6th – 4th Century BC). New Approaches and Digital Tools. Xanthi.

Tsiafaki et al. 2023: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Yiannis Mourthos, Natasa Michailidou, Domna Sarafopoulou eds. Mythical Journeys in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Xanthi.

Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Amalia Avramidou, Natasa Michailidou, Eirini Chioti, Christina Markou, Yiannis Mourthos, Konstantina Tsonaka, Kostas Stavroglou, Markos Dimitsas and Guentcho Banev. “ I parousía tis attikís keramikís stin arkháia Thráki mésa apó to érgo AtticPOT”. In: *To Arkhaiologyikó Érgo sti Makedonía kai sti Thráki*, 33i Epistimonikí Sinántisi (2019-2020), 22-24 Aprilíou 2021, Thessaloniki.

Tsiafaki et al. forthcoming: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Yiannis Mourthos, Natasa Michailidou, Meliana Karta. As far as Attic vases go: studying the presence of Athenian Kerameikos in ancient Thrace.

In: European Association of Archaeologists (EAA) Annual Meeting, Budapest, 31 August – 3 September 2022.

Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2006: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Vassilis Evangelidis. GIS as an Interpretative Tool in Greek Archaeological Research. In: Proceedings of the GIS Research UK 14th Annual Conference, GISRUK 2006, 5th-7th April, 2006, School of Geography, University of Nottingham, Great Britain (eds G. Priestnall, P. Aplin). UK, 328-333.

Tsiafaki and Evangelidis 2022: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Vassilis Evangelidis. Exploring Rivers and Ancient Settlements in Aegean Thrace through Spatial Technology. In: *The Riverlands of Aegean Thrace: Production, Consumption and Exploitation of the Natural and Cultural Landscapes | River Valleys and Regional Economies: Panel 2.4 | Panel 2.7*, Heidelberg: Propylaeum, 2022 (Archaeology and Economy in the Ancient World: Proceedings of the 19th International Congress of Classical Archaeology, Cologne/Bonn 2018, Band 6) (ed. Euridike Kefalidou). Heidelberg, 45-61.

Tsiafaki and Michailidou 2019: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Natasa Michailidou. Ways to Cope with the Scientific ARENA: Taking the Results of Archaeological Research a Step Further. In: Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies Held in Vienna, Austria November 2018, 1-9.

Tsiafaki, Michailidou, Chioti 2020: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Natasa Michailidou, Eirini Chioti. AtticPOT: éna psiphiaikó ergalío yia tin erminía tis parousías attikón angíon stin arkháia Thráki. In: 3o Panelínio Sinédrio Psiphioipiísis Politistikís Klironomiás – EuroMed 2019, Athína, 25-27 Septemvríou 2019. *Aθήνα*, 156-167.

Tsiafaki, Mourthos, Michailidou forthcoming: Tsiafaki, Despoina, Yiannis, Mourthos Natasa Michailidou. Old data new tools: 4th century lekythoi in ancient Thrace through AtticPOT. In: International Workshop “Greek Pottery of the 4th cent. B.C. New Data from the Field”, 29 November 2021, École Française d’Athènes.

Vacalopoulou et al. 2023: Vacalopoulou, Anna, Anna Mastrogianni, Charilaos Michalopoulos, Despoina Tsiafaki, Natasa Michailidou, Ioannis Mourthos, Paraskevi Botini, Gregory Stainhaouer. Mythological Itineraries Along the Western Silk Road: Finding Myths in Visits to Eastern Macedonia and Thrace Today. In: *Cities’ Vocabularies and the Sustainable Development of the Silkroads*, SRSTDCH 2021 (eds. S. Kostopoulou, G. Herrera-Franco, J. Wood, K. Al-Kodmany), Cham, 139-153.

Използване на дигитални инструменти в изследванията на Древна Тракия

Деспина Циафаки, Янис Муртос,
Мелпомени Карта, Натаса Михайлиду

Отделът за култура и творчески индустрии на Изследователски център Athena в Ксанти (Гърция) се фокусира върху използването на различни дигитални инструменти за археологически изследвания. Чрез различни проекти се използва широк набор от дигитални инструменти за изучаване на историята и археологията на древна Тракия. Въз основа изследването на различни критерии са анализирани разпространението, употребата и културното значение на атическите вази в древна Тракия. Изследването на древните митове и връзката им с тракийския ландшафт показва културния и туристически потенциал на Източна Македония и Тракия. Освен това, използвайки ГИС софтуер, лабораторията AeGIS проучи различни археологически теми чрез използване на символи и инструменти за количествен анализ, както и топлинни карти и инструменти за реконструкция на мрежа.

List of the additional images:

- p. 6 – The door of the tomb of Golyama Kosmatka, Archaeological field survey in 2009 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 13 – Abraham Ortelius' map of ancient Thrace dated to 1585. Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons. <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Thraciae-veteris-typvs.jpg>
- p. 14 – Rock-cut niches at Harmankaya, Bivoljane village, Momchilgrad Municipality, Photo G. Nekhrizov, 2024.
- p. 20 – Frescoes from the ceiling of the Ostrusha Tomb, Archaeological field survey in 2009 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 25 – Votive relief from Piraeus, depicting the Thracian Goddess Bendis (400-375 BC), British Museum. Andres Rueda, CC BY 2.0, via Wikimedia Commons. [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Marble_Votive_Relief_Dedicated_to_the_Goddess_Artemis_Bendis_\(Made_in_Athens_about_400-375_BC,_From_Piraeus,Attica\)_-_British_Museum.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Marble_Votive_Relief_Dedicated_to_the_Goddess_Artemis_Bendis_(Made_in_Athens_about_400-375_BC,_From_Piraeus,Attica)_-_British_Museum.jpg)
- p. 26 – Amphora-shaped vessel from Early Iron age. Gluhite kamani rock-cut complex, Lyubimets Municipality. Excavations in 2016 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. RHM Haskovo. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov
- p. 33 - Bust of Aristotle. Marble, Roman copy after a Greek bronze original by Lysippos from 330 BC; the alabaster mantle is a modern addition; inv. no 8575; Museo Nazionale Romano, Rome (Italy). Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons CC BY-SA 4.0. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Aristotle_Altemps_Inv8575.jpg
- p. 45 – Map of the Northern Aegean, by the Venetian cartographer Vincenzo Maria Coronelli, ca. 1697. Public domain via Wikimedia Commons. https://commons.m.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Arcipelago,_Northern_Aegean_map_by_V.M.Coronelli,_1697.gif#file
- p. 46 – Detail of the fresco decoration in the burial chamber of the Alexandrovo Tomb. Non-destructive investigations and photographing of the mural paintings in 2019, under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 53 - DEM of the tomb at Mishkova Niva, Malko Tarnovo. Photos and orthophoto mosaic processed by J. Tzvetkova under the projects 80-10-118/2021 at SU and “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 54 – The tomb at Buzovgrad village, Kazanlak Municipality. Archaeological excavations of G. Nekhrizov in 2012. Photo G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 61 – Burial mounds in the Kazanlak valley. Field survey in 2009 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov/A. Sobotkova.
- p. 62 – Head of Roman Statue of Fortuna/Tyche from Deultum, RHM Burgas. Orthophoto mosaic processed by S. Sabkova under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KII-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 70 – Detail of the fresco decoration in the burial chamber of the Alexandrovo Tomb. Non-destructive investigations and photographing of the mural paintings in 2019, under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 80 – Roman Mosaic from the basilica of St. Sophia, Sofia. National Archaeological Museum Sofia. Photo V. Stolba in 2022, under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 81 – Oescus (Bulgaria). Temples of the Capitoline Triad (2nd-4th centuries AD). Aerial photo carried out under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020). Photo Iv. Valchev.
- p. 82 – Greek inscription from Malko Tarnovo Historical Museum. Field survey and investigations under the guidance of J. Tzvetkova in 2021 (Project no. 80-10-118/2021 at SU). Photo D. Boteva.
- p. 93 – Drawing of the town of Sozopol (ancient Apollonia Pontica) by Jan Peeters (17th century); 18x33 cm; family archive of Olya Bakardjieva. Courtesy [Dr Stefan Peykov](#) (Digital Archive Thrace – GEOPAN).
- p. 94 – Detail of the fresco decoration in the burial chamber of the copy of Kazanlak Tomb. Archaeological field survey in 2009 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov.

- p. 100 – Greek inscription from Malko Tarnovo Historical Museum. Field survey and investigations under the guidance of J. Tzvetkova in 2021 (Project no. 80-10-118/2021 at SU), Photo D. Boteva.
- p. 107 – Home page in English of the TELAMON project. <https://telamon.uni-sofia.bg/en/> (accessed 20.12.2024).
- p. 108 – Relief from Gramatikovo village, Malko Tarnovo Municipality. Malko Tarnovo History Museum. Field survey and investigations under the guidance of J. Tzvetkova in 2021 (Project no. 80-10-118/2021 at SU), Photo D. Boteva.
- p. 113 – Detail of the Attic red figure pelike, depicting Orpheus among Thracians; ca. 430 BC; British Museum, 1846,0925.10 Cat. Vases E 390. ArchaiOptix, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Manner_of_the_Kleophon_Painter_ARV_1148_7_Orpheus_singing_before_the_Thracians_-_three_draped_youths_%2801%29.jpg
- p. 114 – The funerary bed from the Mezek Tomb with coins placed now-a-days. Photo V. Stolba in 2022, under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 127 – Hemidrachms of the Thracian Chersonese from the Troyanovo coin hoard (Regional History Museum Stara Zagora, Bulgaria; inv. no 3068). Photo J. Tzvetkova.
- p. 128 – Marble relief of the three nymphs from Diocletianopolis (mod. Hisarya), Hisarya Archaeological Museum. Photo D. Boteva in 2023, under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 136 – Detail of the fresco decoration in the burial chamber of the copy of Kazanlak Tomb. Archaeological field survey in 2009 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 148 – The funerary bed (*kline*) from the tomb at Dolno Izvorovo, Kazanlak Municipality. Archaeological excavations of G. Nekhrizov in 2009. Photo G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 157 – The sanctuary from the Iron Age at Ada tepe, Krumovgrad Municipality. Archaeological excavation 2002 under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo archive G. Nekhrizov.
- p. 158 – The pediment from the tomb of Mishkova niva, Malko Tarnovo Historical Museum. Field survey and investigations under the guidance of J. Tzvetkova in 2021 (Project no. 80-10-118/2021 at SU), Photo D. Boteva.
- p. 167 – Mythras relief from RHM Sofia. Photo V. Stolba in 2022, under the project “Measuring Ancient Thrace” (BNSF no. KP-06-H50/3 from 2020).
- p. 168 – Detail of the fresco decoration in the burial chamber of the Alexandrovo Tomb. Non-destructive investigations and photographing of the mural paintings in 2019, under the guidance of G. Nekhrizov. Photo G. Nekhrizov.